

THE ROLE OF ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION AND CULTURE IN HUMAN LIFE

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Abstract

In the article, the role of ecological culture as a factor of Social Development and ecological culture is a new culture of humanity, which determines the value of a person's environmentally healthy behavior, activity and relations between man and the socio-natural environment, which stimulate a higher level of quality. In a broad sense, ecological culture is a new content of human culture.

Keywords

ecological culture, environment, value, culture, behavior, socio-natural environment, nature, philosophical cultural scientists, ecological crisis, New ecocentric, science, art, Customs and traditions.

Introduction

Environmental education. The word ecology, meaning "roof" or "house", was first introduced into science by the German scientist Ernest Gekkel. The science of ecology is present in crop ecology, zooecology, soil ecology, human ecology, etc. The science of ecology studies the living conditions or norms of one or more selected objects and helps to determine the optimal level of living. Work in this direction will convey to us environmental knowledge, but humanity will not be limited by it. At the request of the period, again requires work in another direction. It is also a matter of environmental education.

Main part

Environmental education is necessarily formed on the basis of environmental knowledge, but it also has its own characteristics. Environmental education works on the issue of the formation of a correct, rational attitude towards nature in a person and sets itself the goal of forming an ecological culture in students. The content of environmental education includes environmental awareness, environmental emotions (attitudes towards nature, people, life). Thus, environmental education plays an important role in a person's Life, Society,

Homeland. In addition to acquiring environmental knowledge, it will be necessary to form environmental relations for the formation of environmental education.

Environmental relations: attitude to life. Nurture a sense of integrity. Nurture a sense of responsibility. Components such as feeling the beauties of nature can be included. Environmental education was viewed with deep responsibility not only today, but also by our ancestors. For example, the environment - in order not to pollute the environment, separate pits were dug for garbage disposal, waste disposal, they dug toilets in a place away from the waters of ditches, ponds, Springs, cut down dried trees for various needs, tormenting animals, destroying a bird's nest, counting sins. In this regard, the family says "do not spit in the water, do not dirty it, because all animals drink it and enjoy it", "do not break the branch of a flowering fruit tree, it bears fruit, eat it yourself kilasan", "do not take unripe grapes, if you break it, a big sin will be work, for he has the share of the faithful among his people". The environmental education and education system is continued in kindergartens, general education schools, later educational stages and in labor communities. In this place, through life examples, at the moment, low environmental literacy in families is promoted. For example, now many people continue to feed their cattle in cultivated areas, in gardens, even tied to fruit and ornamental trees. After all, in the past, special herdsmen were kept in the care of our people. Or those who have a good fortune will be fed lots in turn. For this, as now, animals were grazed not on the land they encountered, but on isolated pastures. Or when going out to family rest, the grass was not laid, glass fractures in the slopes, food residues were not abandoned.

There was no harm to trees, the world of plants, animals. The content of the preparation of environmental education includes: the environment and its impact on the spiritual world of the individual; determining nature and its significance; cooperation of the school and family in the development of love for nature; increasing their interest in greening the courtyard of their own municipality, city, village and school, caring for even plants in the classroom; Environmental Protection; In the ecological education of young people, the revival of national traditions and customs, the strengthening of attention to them. In the family, at school, teaching to honor Nature, Plants and fauna, caring for animals and birds; from the history of mankind, it is known that a healthy society is created only by a healthy environment. Ensuring a bright future of Uzbekistan is reflected in the law "on education", the National Training Program. In this regard, one of the tasks set before primary education is the formation of students' conscious attitude to the environment, successfully solving such a task requires teachers to have deep

knowledge in their field, a high environmental culture, to be creative, to conduct training on the basis of pedagogical technologies. A teacher with such qualities should bring up a harmonious personality, who has a deep grasp of the theoretical knowledge of Environmental Education, knows the secret of processes in nature, understands its socio-economic and spiritual significance, and will have a conscious attitude towards nature. Various manuals, media, textbooks, extracurricular activities are an important resource for the teacher to teach.

Education of students in the spirit of respect for nature does not consist only in the course of the lesson. The lesson is time-limited, in which many important environmental knowledge cannot be taught to students. Extracurricular activities, on the other hand, are not limited in terms of time. The development of environmental knowledge acquired by students in the course of the lesson in extracurricular activities gives an effective result. Extracurricular activities in educating elementary students in the spirit of respect for nature are a continuation of the knowledge that students receive in the course of the lesson, and they complement the content and integrate it into one whole process. Extracurricular activities are an additional and free type of education that allows you to expand the creative activities of students. Educational trips are of great importance in the study of the world around us. Travel lessons as a form of organizing educational work are an important tool in the environmental education of students. In the process of observing nature, cognitive activity is formed, students' perception of the interaction of living and inanimate nature, flora and fauna is expanded. Communication with nature evokes beautiful emotions in readers. Students are fascinated by green grass, bird wandering, butterfly flight, and the variety of trees and plants.

The purpose of organizing trips is to study the tree species, vegetation, insects, bird lifestyles in the garden.

When the assignments are completed, the teacher summarizes the results of the travel lesson and gives the students a task to the House. Task Home: write an essay about the impressions you received from the trip. On the basis of travel lessons, students should love the beauties of nature, get aesthetic pleasure from them; deeply study the interaction between nature and society, as well as the consequences of the impact of human activity on nature; focus on educating students in the spirit of respect for nature. In the process of travel, an unconventional lesson: role-playing game, action game, observation methods are used. Such a lesson will increase students' interest in the environment. They are brought up in the spirit of a conscious attitude to nature. We organized trips with

3rd graders on topics such as "Love Nature, duck", "birds are our friend", "I love nature". The importance of extracurricular work in the disciplines of "the world around us", "Natural Science" and its socially useful direction. During extracurricular hours with students, various activities are held: travel work, early times, extracurricular studies, circles of interest and other activities. These works arouse students' interest in knowing nature under the guidance of a teacher. Extracurricular work in Natural Science provides an opportunity to expand, deepen and clarify the knowledge gained in the lessons, arouse interest in the study of nature, develop students' activity and attitude to respect for nature, organize this time. Extracurricular naturalist work is also of educational importance in educating primary school students in the spirit of respect for nature, as it affects the behavior of students. They form a view of the material world and a culture of Labor, develop interest in knowledge and independent observation skills, educate public perception and love of nature. The established extracurricular activities in natural science are one of the tools for the comprehensive development of the student's personality. Content of extracurricular activities. Extracurricular work in Natural Science includes diverse activities related to the study and veneration of nature, plant cultivation, animal care. These activities should not repeat the lessons and should be based only on the knowledge gained in the lessons.

Students should focus their attention on nature, as well as observations on the lively corner of the school and the educational and experimental area; organize socio-useful work on the greening of the street and school, on the protection of birds and the fight against agricultural pests. Practical work in nature should be accompanied by observations and reading related books. In order for extracurricular work to proceed intensively, it is necessary to carefully consider the forms of its organization. Extracurricular activities should be divided into three groups. The first group the second group the third group is a group of Public Works, events that cover many students. Circle work carried out within the framework of limited pupils. Work conducted with some students interested in studying t abiat. Public activities include screening motion pictures, conducting nature tours, organizing an exhibition of early days, student work, as well as holding events (Harvest Day, Garden Week, tree holding week, Bird Day, etc. Group training includes young geographers, young naturalists, circle work. Individual sessions produce mural newspapers, albums; live nature corner and work in the school study-experience space, nature; extracurricular reading and selection of materials of the content of Natural Science for the information corner

include analysis to the journals "Young Naturalist" about nature, readers to Popular Science books.

All types of extracurricular activities should complement and improve each other when educating elementary school students in the spirit of respect for nature. When performing an Individual task or a teacher's recommendation, a certain interest should be aroused. Having identified similar interests in several students, the teacher combines them into a circle. Such associations should remain the organizational center of mass extracurricular activities, in order to successfully pass them, various preparatory work and a large number of participants are needed. When educating students in the spirit of respect for nature, extracurricular work should be diverse in terms of organizational form, content, methods of conducting. Its content will not be somehow constant. It depends on the composition, age, interest and need of the students, the school's natural enclosure, season of the Year, room and facilities. An approximate list of works that primary school teachers should use is as follows: observations in nature, identification of the causes of natural phenomena; trips to the Museum of local lore (Nature Museum), places where fossil resources are obtained, fields and farms with the formalization of collected materials; collection and formalization of natural material, collection, herbarium, layout, modeling; drawing up a; reading Popular Science, natural science literature, articles published in the journals "Bud", "young naturalist" as a team; organizing a lively nature corner, conducting experiments on plants and animals, as well as conducting experiments and observations on the site of a school reception; viewing motion pictures, diafilms, diapositives in the content of Natural Science; getting acquainted with exhibitions of achievements of the national economy; k.) participation; acquaintance with animals of the city of Tashkent and the city of Termez, Surkhandarya Region; Nature Protection, conversations about the benefits and importance of plants and animals in a person's life; socio-beneficial works aimed at honoring nature, conservation of greenery, conducting trees and shrubs and their care, collecting seeds, fruits of foreign and cultural plants, weeds, fields, plums, Gardens, forest pest control, protection of beneficial animals; equip a natural science room, a local history corner, exhibitions, a nature corner; make simple visual weapons out of natural material, organize an exhibition of students' work; collect material for Wall newspapers and albums; release news stories such as the wall newspaper, "about Mother Nature", "honor Nature", "read about nature" and the like; collect literature for further reading on the topics of The teacher plans in advance the methods and methods of extracurricular natural science work in the

upbringing of nature in the spirit of respect, is involved in various types of student activities

makes. The success of extracurricular activities largely depends on the correct choice of material for each activity, the structure plan and methodology of its conduct, as well as the active participation of students in the intended events.

Conclusion

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